

1 **Title**

2 **An Environmental Health Vocabulary and its Semi-Automated Curation Workflow**

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52 The data that support this work are openly available in HAWC [Health Assessment Workspace](#)
53 [Collaborative \(HAWC\) \(epa.gov\)](#) and github repo [GitHub - USEPA/ehv: A repository for curation and](#)
54 [related activities of the Environmental Health Vocabulary \(EHV\)](#). The Environmental Health Vocabulary is
55 available at: <https://hawc.epa.gov/vocab/ehv/>.

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63 **Abstract**~~BSTRACT~~

64 **Background:** The environmental health vocabulary (EHV) ~~represents a manually curated controlled~~
65 ~~terminologies vocabulary~~ developed by the US Environmental Protection Agency's (EPA) Chemical
66 Pollutant Assessment Division (CPAD) ~~for standardizing reporting of health effect information.~~
67 ~~Recognizing that manual data curation is a resource bottleneck, a semi-automated curation workflow~~
68 ~~was realized within the Office of Research and Development (ORD). The purpose of the EHV is to~~
69 ~~standardize the data supporting human health chemical assessments to promote accessibility and data~~
70 ~~exchange. The EHV is specific to the EPA's CPAD and was initially developed by manual review and~~
71 ~~curation of terms extracted into the EPA Health Assessment Collaborative (HAWC). Recognizing that the~~
72 ~~current manual curation approach to updating the EHV does not scale with the rate new terms are~~
73 ~~entered into HAWC and the need to update existing HAWC terms with additional metadata, a semi-~~
74 ~~automated curation workflow was realized.~~

75 **Objectives:** The objectives of this work are to ~~describe the manual creation of the EHV and improve the~~
76 ~~efficiency of manual data curation by implementing~~ describe the manual creation of the current EHV, a
77 ~~new semi-automated~~ new curation workflow method for adding new terms to the EHV, and a method to
78 update existing EHV terms with metadata and definitions using one semi-automated curation workflow.
79 An additional objective is to ~~that minimizes~~ minimize the requirement of manual review and analysis of
80 ~~extracted terms by applying~~ using a sequence of computational text analysis and quality assurance (QA)
81 steps with a high level of accuracy.

82 **Methods:** ~~To facilitate semi-automated curation~~ To create the EHV, terms extracted into HAWC were
83 ~~collected and manually curated into a hierarchical controlled vocabulary fit for use by EPA CPAD during~~
84 ~~assessment development. The new semi-automated workflow adds computational steps to add new~~
85 ~~terms, update existing terms, and add metadata. Specifically, the new EHV curation process includes~~
86 ~~application of a sequence of computational text analysis and manual steps as follows 1) were developed.~~
87 ~~Described are 1) a series of computational~~ text processing steps to normalize and match extracted
88 terms and identify matches to the existing EHV endpoints; 2) manual a quality assurance (QA) step of
89 the computationally identified matches using hierarchical data to help bin terms; 3) a manual review of
90 unmatched terms to identify possible matches not identified by computational processing; and 4)
91 curation of the EHV data, including the standardization of terms, that includes completion of missing
92 hierarchical data and related metadata.

93 **Discussion:** ~~The data standardization strategy described here promotes consistent and searchable~~
94 ~~description of the study findings utilizing the EHV, a controlled vocabulary that is freely accessible to the~~
95 ~~environmental health community. The EHV was manually created to promote data aggregation,~~
96 ~~integration, accessibility and transparent data exchange across EPA partners by normalizing the data~~
97 ~~making study extracted into the EPA Health Assessment Workplace Collaborative (HAWC). data machine~~
98 ~~actionable and therefore easily aggregated, updated, and disseminated. The EHV was previously limited~~
99 ~~by manual curation. The workflow described here removes the transitions manual curation bottleneck by~~
100 ~~transforming data curation into a streamlined semi-automated process workflow powered by using~~
101 ~~computational text processing steps with a human in the loop. This semi-automated curation method~~
102 ~~offers several advantages to the environmental health community including (but not limited to)~~
103 ~~efficiency by automating repeating data management tasks, scalability to a large volume of terms and~~
104 ~~terminology resources, and better integration with other data sets and artificial intelligence (AI) and~~
105 ~~machine learning (ML) models. Implementation of standards are semantic solutions to data reporting~~
106 ~~that promote harmonization in the environmental health community and create more opportunities for~~
107 ~~sharing extracted content.~~

108 **Introduction**~~NTRODUCTION~~

109 The U.S. Environmental Protection Agency's (EPA) Chemical Pollutant Assessment Division
110 (CPAD) utilizes systemic search, selection, and coding strategies to produce searchable databases of
111 study data. These databases include data and descriptive metadata that helps the reader evaluate the
112 reliability and quality of the evidence used in human health chemical assessment. The U.S. EPA has been
113 summarizing these data using data extraction templates, such as those implemented in systematic
114 evidence maps (SEMs) (Thayer et. al., 2022). Data extraction ~~Fi~~ templates promote consistency across the
115 extracted study data and foster data accessibility and ~~data~~ exchange across the environmental health
116 community. SEMs developed from these templates expedite the assessment process, and can be
117 defined as "A comprehensive summary of the characteristics and availability of evidence as it relates to
118 broader themes of policy or decision-making relevance" (Wolffe et. al., 2019). ~~Templates such as those~~
119 ~~used in SEMs promote transparency of and accessibility to the metadata and data~~ without presenting
120 conclusions on the science ~~and promote a clear and consistent interpretation of the available evidence~~
121 supporting chemical human health and environmental assessments (U.S. EPA, 2022). Increased
122 utilization of template formats ~~that make the study data freely available, transparent, and easily~~
123 ~~updatable across the environmental health field has the potential to increase transparency~~
124 ~~and streamline data exchange and promote efficiencies and cost savings for all partners invested in y for~~
125 data gathering, problem formulation, and evidence surveillance. Yet, data extraction and reporting are
126 resource intensive due to the lack of structure and semantic variability in the reported data. one of the
127 largest hurdles is the manual review, extraction, and curation of data from PDF that are key to efficiently
128 making the study data freely available, transparent, and easily updatable.

129 Data extraction is implemented in the U.S. EPA's version of Health Assessment Workplace
130 Collaborative (HAWC) (<https://hawcprd.epa.gov/portal/>) as described in the U.S. EPA IRIS Handbook
131 (U.S. EPA, 2022). Part of the data extraction strategy includes application of agreed (meta)data
132 standards, ~~vocabularies and ontologies~~ as proactive solutions to normalize and management and
133 ~~accessibility within~~ standardize the complex terminologies used to describe the environmental health
134 science domain. ~~Ontologies and vocabularies are useful to standardize variables reported into data~~
135 ~~extraction template fields (species, strain sex, chemical, route, duration, dose, etc.). These standards are~~
136 ~~used to control and make machine actionable the language extracted into template fields and stored~~
137 ~~into data repositories. These standards ensure data can be aggregated into SEMs and ensure data~~
138 consistency, quality and formats amenable to data exchange. Ontologies are also useful for mapping

139 variables and fields across data repository models and relating data across knowledge domains (e.g.
140 animal, human, ecological toxicology).

141 ~~Agreed upon practices for data extraction were included in the data extraction workflow used~~
142 ~~by the U.S. EPA HAWC to overcome semantic challenges due to variation in language.~~ For example,
143 there are many textual descriptions data extractors could use to report the study details and findings for
144 a particular finding or health effect (e.g. alanine transferase ~ Serum Glutamate-Pyruvate Transaminase
145 ~ Alanine Aminotransferase ~ Serum Glutamic-Pyruvic Transaminase ~ Alanine Transaminase ~ serum
146 glutamate pyruvate transaminase). While these are related, they do not match, leading to
147 inconsistencies that, if not standardized, complicate aggregation and integration of the findings linked
148 within and across chemical assessments and other human and environmental health data.

149 ~~Therefore, to remove inconsistency from the data extracted within these fields, the data~~
150 ~~extraction implementation in EPA HAWC includes a standardization and digitization step. For most data~~
151 ~~fields, the data are normalized to field specific picklists curated by PhD level scientists with expertise in~~
152 ~~assessment development (U.S. EPA, 2022). This normalization process promotes consistency, while~~
153 ~~facilitating access to, and reuse of the extracted study findings and associated metadata. Of all the data~~
154 ~~extraction fields, the “Endpoint” field is the broadest and the most variable. The “Endpoint” field is~~
155 ~~defined in the U.S. EPA IRIS Handbook glossary as: An observable or measurable biological change used~~
156 ~~as an index of a potential health effect of a chemical exposure. Often, “endpoint” is used when describing~~
157 ~~animal toxicological findings while outcome” is used when describing human findings. Endpoint may also~~
158 ~~be referred to as effect. (U.S. EPA, 2022).~~

159 ~~Standardization of the “Endpoint” field (meta)data is a significant semantic challenge because~~
160 ~~the number of available endpoints is vast and there are usually multiple ways to describe the term.~~

161 Therefore, the Environmental Health Vocabulary (EHV) was created by EPA CPAD in 2022 to both
162 normalize the reported terminology and standardize endpoint terms extracted into HAWC.

163 Standardization of the “Endpoint” field (meta)data is a significant semantic challenge because the
164 number of available endpoints is vast and, as described above, there are usually multiple ways to
165 describe the term. The EHV is a standardized and controlled vocabulary for reporting animal health
166 effects of environmental chemical exposure. A controlled vocabulary is an organized collection of words
167 and phrases that typically includes preferred terms that are non-redundant, unambiguous, can be
168 indexed, are machine readable and can be used to search a content management system through query
169 (see <https://www.niehs.nih.gov/research/programs/ehlc/resources> for additional information and
170 resources). The EHV is designed to have a five-tier hierarchical order such that: system->organ->effect-

171 >effect subtype->endpoint/outcome (Figure 1A). The hierarchy supports aggregation of endpoints into
172 visual representations that can be categorized at the system, organ, effect, or effect subtype level
173 depending on assessment need. The EHV can be used as a reference for ~~standardizing reporting of~~
174 health effect information primarily from animal bioassay studies and is currently implemented in HAWC.
175 The EHV is user enabled and accessible in the HAWC data entry screen where EHV terms are available
176 for selection by name or unique ID.

177 The EHV was developed through a manual curation effort of terms and phrases extracted from
178 the peer-reviewed animal toxicology literature (identified during assessment developed based on
179 Population, Exposure, Comparator, and Outcome criteria, PECO) into HAWC as part of the chemical
180 assessment workflow (see Chapter 5. Extraction and Display of results from epidemiological and
181 toxicological studies, U.S. EPA. 2022). In the current [EHV](#), the curation process consisted of 100% manual
182 review of the terms extracted into HAWC by PhD level experts with assessment development
183 experience. The manual process involved download of HAWC extracted terms, manual review
184 supplemented by consultation with domain experts as needed, look-up from terminology resources
185 such as Clinical Data Interchange Standard for Exchange of Nonclinical Data (CDISC SEND, [2023](#))
186 Controlled Terminology (<https://www.cdisc.org/standards/foundational/send>), Unified Medical
187 Language Syntax (UMLS, [2023](#)) (<https://uts.nlm.nih.gov/uts/umls/home>), and ([Makris et. al., 2009](#))
188 ~~Makris et. al., 2009~~ [for developmental and reproductive outcomes](#) and comparison to prior health
189 endpoint mappings from the U.S. EPA's Integrated Science Assessments. [As described above, t](#)The exact
190 organization of the EHV and terms within the EHV were developed to improve the efficiency of data
191 ~~reporting,~~ aggregation, [integration](#), and filtering for visualization of the findings that support animal
192 evidence synthesis and visualization in human [and environmental](#) health assessments. For example, the
193 EHV enables data aggregation and visualization across multiple studies by health system, organ, and
194 endpoint (Figure 1B). The EHV is optional, allowing for free text data entry when a newly extracted term
195 is not available in the EHV. Approximately half of all public EPA HAWC projects are using the EHV, and
196 within EHV enabled projects, approximately 37,000 endpoints were extracted ([last updated December](#)
197 [2024](#)). Of those, approximately 70% of all endpoints used the EHV directly, with 30% using custom user
198 defined terms.

199 Manual curation is a time-consuming ~~data extraction process~~ ~~process~~ requiring expert technical
200 insight. [Therefore, the objective of the EHV Curation Workflow described herein is to minimize the](#)
201 [requirement of manual review and analysis of extracted terms by applying a sequence of computational](#)
202 [text analysis steps with a high level of accuracy. Further, For example, extracted terms may be repeated](#)

203 ~~in datasets because of differences in punctuation, case, word order, or extraneous characters, and they~~
204 ~~may already be represented in the EHV by a synonymous term.~~ Several steps in the curation workflow
205 (term matching and look-up) include text mining steps can be scaled-up and semi-automated using
206 computational approaches **to streamline the data extraction process.** ~~Therefore, the objective of the~~
207 ~~EHV Curation Workflow described herein is to minimize the requirement of manual review and analysis~~
208 ~~of extracted terms by applying a sequence of computational text analysis steps with a high level of~~
209 ~~accuracy.~~

210 **Methodology**

211 **Workflow Overview**

212 The following terms associated with the
213 workflow described here are defined in Box 1: Term,
214 curate, standardize (or normalize), match (matching),
215 and cleanup. Terms without a confirmed match are
216 candidates for further manual review and possible
217 addition to the EHV.

218 Because terms in the EHV are organized within
219 a five-level hierarchy (i.e., organ system, organ, effect,
220 sub-effect, and endpoint), curation involves normalizing
221 the endpoint terms and then the associated terms
222 falling into each of the other four hierarchical levels.
223 Curation also involves completing missing definitions
224 and other metadata using Unified Medical Language
225 System (UMLS), Clinical Data Interchange Standards
226 Consortium - Standard Exchange for Nonclinical Data
227 (CDISC-SEND), Medical Subject Headings (MeSH),
228 Logical Observation Identifiers Names and Codes
229 (LOINC), Uber-anatomy ontology (UBERON), etc.

230 The EHV ~~c~~uration ~~w~~orkflow is intended to
231 semi-automate curation steps while including a human
232 in the loop. Terms are initially processed and grouped
233 based on whether the term is a new or existing term.

234 The specific details and subsequent steps of the workflow are described below.

Box 1: Useful Definitions

Term – A word, phrase, or variant representing something specific and presented as a single datapoint. For this project, terms are health endpoint names.

Curate – To process a dataset of terms by removing extraneous terms or records, normalizing inconsistencies among datapoints within a single field, and adding or correcting required datapoints, identifiers, or metadata.

Standardize (or normalize) – To reduce an array of terms that all represent the same thing or concept to a single representative term that is used preferentially.

Match (matching) – Computationally or manually determining that a term is equivalent in meaning to a standardized term or that a term can be associated with an established corresponding identifier (ID).

Cleanup – Computationally or manually removing extraneous spaces, characters, or punctuation from a collection of terms.

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235 **Methodology**

236 At high level, the workflow compares terms extracted into HAWC to the existing EHV and sorts
237 ~~them through the workflow depending on if they match or do not match the EHV terms into three~~
238 ~~groups. Group 1 terms are extracted HAWC terms. Group 1 terms Terms that do not match~~ are
239 candidates for additional curation and possible addition to the EHV. ~~Group 2 terms are~~ terms extracted
240 into HAWC ~~are identified as matches that are already represented in the EHV (EHV matches). A term is~~
241 ~~determined to be represented in the EHV~~ if the exact term is already in the EHV or ~~if~~ the EHV has a
242 synonym, another term, or phrase that represents the same concept. ~~Terms in Group 2 enter QA/QC.~~
243 Any synonymous matching terms and phrases can be used to refine the efficiency of the workflow when
244 applied to future sets of extracted terms. These terms are compiled into a “cumulative equivalents
245 dataset”. ~~Matching terms enter QA/QC. Group 3 terms are~~ terms that do not match ~~the EHV a term~~
246 after the ~~computational t~~Text ~~p~~Processing step ~~proceed to manual~~ and ~~require~~ manual review ~~before~~
247 ~~QA/QC.~~

248 Figure 2 provides an overview of the EHV Curation Workflow for terms extracted into HAWC.

249 The workflow begins on the left with a set of HAWC extracted terms . ~~Term group will determine~~
250 ~~necessary stages of processing required in the EHV Curation Workflow.~~

251 The workflow includes four distinct stages:

- 252 1. **Computational text processing** to clean-up extracted terms (e.g., remove punctuation and
253 extraneous characters) and identify matches to existing EHV terms.
- 254 2. **QA of the computationally identified matches**, including the use of hierarchical data to aid in
255 binning terms and manual QA review.
- 256 3. **Manual review and matching** of unmatched terms to identify additional matches that were not
257 identified by computational processing.
- 258 4. **Curation of EHV data**, including the normalization of terms and completion of hierarchical data
259 and metadata.

260 Each of these stages are discussed in more detail in the sections below.

261 **Computational Processing**

262 The ~~c~~Computational ~~p~~Processing stage within the workflow is shown in Figure 1 by the yellow
263 rectangular boxes. As the name implies, computational processing is carried out with a series of Python
264 scripts available in the GitHub Repo. To run these specific scripts without modification, the input data
265 must be formatted consistently .

266 Four steps are carried out within this stage:

- 267 • Text pre-processing
- 268 • Exact string matching
- 269 • Rules based matching; and
- 270 • SciSpacy ([Neuman et. al., 2019https://allenai.github.io/scispacy/](https://allenai.github.io/scispacy/)), a Python package containing
- 271 spaCy (<https://spacy.io/> models for processing biomedical, scientific or clinical text entity
- 272 matching.

273 All steps are applied to terms extracted into HAWC and input into a consistent file format. Note that
274 MS Excel is the file type used in this workflow so any change in file type will require update to the
275 scripts). Each of the scripts uses the [pandas](#) (V2.2.3) Python library to read the Excel information as a
276 data frame. Several functions are written in each of the scripts that can be applied to a column using
277 panda's "apply" method. Other scripts may be written as loops that utilize panda's iterrows method of
278 iterating. To rerun the scripts, a user supplies the data files (the terms extracted into HAWC and the EHV
279 inputs as MS Excel spreadsheets) and updates the scripts to the correct file paths to the data file(s).
280 (Note that example data files are provided in the GitHub repo.) The column names need to match the
281 original column names or be updated throughout the script. When data are transformed by the scripts,
282 the resulting text is copied to a new column so that the original and transformed data can be viewed
283 side-by-side for documentation and QA.

284 **Text Pre-Processing**

285 The goal of text pre-processing is to enhance the machine readability of the extracted terms for the
286 subsequent steps. That is, the terms are "cleaned up" to improve the efficiency with which they can be
287 matched to the EHV. The pre-processing code applies distinct transformations to achieve this goal:

- 288 • Numeric codes at the end of a string, often starting with "XXX" or numbers alone, are removed.
- 289 • Punctuation is separated from text characters by adding spaces before and after each
290 punctuation character. Dashes or hyphens within the text are replaced with spaces.
- 291 • Leading and trailing spaces (i.e., spaces preceding and following the text, respectively) are
292 removed and extraneous spaces within the text are replaced with a single space.
- 293 • All text characters are converted to lowercase to avoid case-related discrepancies during
294 matching.
- 295 • Parentheses and brackets are removed, along with their contents, to minimize extraneous
296 information that may interfere with matching.
- 297 • Words are lemmatized, i.e., reduced to their base form.

298 The resulting cleaned text is stored in the "1_cleaned" column of the Excel dataset. Specific
 299 examples for of text preprocessing of the terms "Alanine Aminotransferase", "Excitation", and "Live
 300 Fetuses/ Litter" are given in Table 1.

301 **Table 1. Text Preprocessing of HAWC Extracted Terms**

HAWC Extracted Term		Text Preprocessed
HAWC_ID	name	1_cleaned
7713	Alanine Aminotransferase	alanine aminotransferase
1570	Excitation	excitation
152	Live Fetuses/ Litter	live fetuses / litter

302

303 **Exact String Matching**

304 After pre-processing, the exact string-check step searches for an exact match in the EHV for
 305 each HAWC extracted term. This step uses the endpoint terms only; hierarchical data, definitions or
 306 other contextual information is not used. Results are stored in the "EHV_ID" and "Endpoint" columns.
 307 When a match is identified, the EHV ID and Endpoint name are added to the "EHV_ID" and "Endpoint"
 308 columns, respectively. term is added into the original Excel file as shown in Table 2 (note that if there is
 309 no match the entry will be blank).

310 **Table 2. Text Preprocessing and Exact String Matching**

AWC Extracted Term		Text Preprocessed	Exact String Matching	
HAWC_ID	Name	1_cleaned	EHV_ID	Endpoint
7713	Alanine Aminotransferase	alanine aminotransferase	2317	Alanine Aminotransferase (ALT)
1570	Excitation	excitation		
152	Live Fetuses/ Litter	live fetuses / litter	1740	Live Fetuses/ Litter

311

312 **Rules-based Matching**

313 The rules-based matching step uses text analysis algorithms to identify matching endpoint terms
 314 when the HAWC extracted terms do not match the EHV term. The algorithms find matches by evaluating
 315 specific words or phrases and synonyms of those words and phrases. Extracted terms are matched to
 316 synonymous terms identified with the Natural Language Toolkit (NLTK, V3.9.1) Python library (Bird et.
 317 al., 2009). Via a separate script, synonyms for individual words and phrases are obtained using functions
 318 in NLTK through its WordNet module, which is based on a database of English words and conceptual

relationships between words such as antonyms and synonyms. Synonyms identified by NLTK resources are exported as a Python dictionary for use in rules-based matching. The script then searches for matches between words as well as between words and their synonyms. When a match is found (either exact match or through a synonym), the EHV ID and Endpoint name are added to the columns “EHV_ID” and “Endpoint”, respectively. Table 2 shows the results of the **rRules bBased mMatching** of HAWC extracted terms. If no match is found the cell is blank.

Table 2. Text Preprocessing , Exact String Matching, and Rules-Based Matching of HAWC Extracted Terms

AWC Extracted Term		Text Preprocessed	Exact String Matching		Rules Based Matching	
HAWC_ID	Name	1_cleaned	EHV_ID	Endpoint	EHV_ID	Endpoint
7713	Alanine Aminotransferase	alanine aminotransferase	2317	Alanine Aminotransferase (ALT)	2317	Alanine Aminotransferase (ALT)
1570	Excitation	excitation			3213	Inflammation
152	Live Fetuses/ Litter	live fetuses / litter	1740	Live Fetuses / Litter		

SciSpacy Entity Matching

The final step of the Computational Processing stage of the workflow leverages the capabilities of SciSpacy, an open-source software library for advanced natural language processing. SciSpacy is specifically adapted for the analysis of scientific and biomedical text sources (Neuman et.al., 2019). Within the workflow, SciSpacy is used to link the terms in each dataset (i.e., terms extracted into HAWC and EHV terms) to equivalent scientific entities (i.e., concepts). The objective of this step is to map the identified entities within the text to their corresponding Concept Unique Identifiers (CUIs) from the Unified Medical Language System (UMLS) Metathesaurus (Bodenreider, O. 2004). The UMLS Metathesaurus is a comprehensive source of biomedical and health-related concepts, terms, and codes. The "SciSpacy" library employs sophisticated natural language processing techniques to recognize entities within the text that are relevant to the concepts in the biomedical domain. These entities could include medical terms, diseases, drugs, or anatomical structures. Once identified, the library links these entities to specific Concept Unique Identifiers (CUIs) within the UMLS Metathesaurus, providing a standardized way to represent and reference biomedical concepts. Table 3 shows the results of the

342 SciSpacy of HAWC extracted terms. If no match is found the cell is blank. The full results of
 343 computational data processing are available in the GitHub repo.

344 **Table 3. Text Preprocessing , Exact String Matching, Rules-Based Matching, and SciSpacy of HAWC**
 345 **Extracted Terms**

AWC Extracted Term		Text Preprocessed	Exact String Matching		Rules Based Matching		SciSpacy	
HAWC_ID	name	1_cleaned	EHV_ID	Endpoint	EHV_ID	Endpoint	EHV_ID	Endpoint
7713	Alanine Aminotransferase	alanine aminotransferase	2317	Alanine Aminotransferase (ALT) 971	2317	Alanine Aminotransferase (ALT) 971	2317	Alanine Aminotransferase (ALT)
1570	Excitation	excitation			3213	Inflammation 3360		
152	Live Fetuses/Litter	live fetuses / litter	1740	Live Fetuses/Litter			1740	Live Pups Born

346 **QA/QC of Computational Matches**

347 Outputs from the **c**omputational **p**rocessing stage include terms that matched the EHV and
 348 terms that do not match. Terms that match the EHV proceed into the QC stage of the EHV Curation
 349 Workflow. The purpose of this stage is to provide quality assurance (QA/QC) for the computational
 350 matching of the extracted terms to EHV terms. This QA/QC only pertains to terms that have been
 351 identified as matches by the computational processing steps. Terms that were not identified
 352 computationally as matches proceed to full manual review and are evaluated in a separate sequence of
 353 steps that is described under the “Manual Review and Matching” section below.

354 Because hundreds or thousands of extracted terms may be processed through the workflow at
 355 once, the QA/QC review of individual terms can be time consuming. Therefore, to minimize the
 356 resources required to perform QA/QC, the hierarchical data associated with each of the terms are used
 357 to further evaluate the likelihood of correct matching. The inclusion of hierarchical data enables the
 358 terms to be sorted into four groups (i.e., “bins”, Figure 3). Bin 1 represents instances where hierarchical
 359 data are complete and all data matches. Bin 2 represents instances where all data matched, but
 360 hierarchical data are incomplete. With this approach, partial QA/QC can be performed for bins 1 and 2

361 (all data match) whereas full review is required for bins 3 and 4 (data mismatch). This approach
362 minimizes the overall level of effort required for expert-level resources required for manual QA/QC.

363 Hierarchical data are compared and binned electronically based on two factors: (1) whether
364 complete hierarchical data are available for the potential term matches and (2) whether the available
365 hierarchical data match. Hierarchical data are complete only if data are available for all five levels (i.e.,
366 system, organ, effect, sub-effect, and endpoint) in both the EHV and HAWC extracted terms datasets.

367 The EHV and HAWC extracted term datasets are compared electronically and classified as true
368 (matching) or false (non-matching). The true/false classifications are written into the Excel dataset as a
369 new column named "Stg# Match as true (1) of false (0) to aid reviewers in sorting and prioritizing
370 records for QA review. During development of this ~~workflow~~workflow, it was observed that a majority of
371 the terms fell into bins 1 (all data match and hierarchical data were complete) and 3 (data mismatch, but
372 hierarchical data were complete). It was also observed that the data mismatches were mostly due to
373 transposition of hierarchical data fields. For example, effects and sub-effects were often swapped,
374 causing a mismatch. Therefore, the current matching approach ignores the order of the hierarchical
375 levels when evaluating matches. For these bin 3 instances, the assumption is that the hierarchical levels
376 in the EHV are correct. However, QA/QC reviewers should record recommendations to reorder the EHV
377 hierarchical data when appropriate.

378 For the most confidently matched terms in Bins 1 and 2, a single reviewer will review a random
379 sample representing 10 percent of the matched terms. Discrepancies identified by the first reviewer will
380 be reviewed and resolved by a secondary reviewer. If discrepancies are found in more than 25 percent
381 of the high confidence terms sampled, the review steps will be repeated for a second, non-overlapping
382 10 percent sample of the terms. This approach will be repeated until fewer than 5 percent of the terms
383 are identified as discrepancies between reviewers. Based on the performance of the ~~c~~Computational
384 ~~T~~Text -in full scale implementation of the workflow, the proposed QA/QC schema may be adjusted to
385 appropriately balance quality control and the level of effort required for manual review. A similar
386 approach will be used for the less confidently matched terms in bins 3 and 4 except the reviewer will
387 review 20 percent of the terms Computationally Matched to the EHV. -If discrepancies arise during
388 QA/QC that cannot be resolved by the primary and secondary reviewers, those terms will be classified as
389 ambiguous and will proceed to expert manual review.

390 **TABLE 4. PROPOSED SCHEMA FOR MANUAL EXPERT QA/QC OF COMPUTATIONALLY MATCHED TERMS**

Bin	Hierarchical Data are Complete?	Hierarchical Data Match?	Matching Confidence	QA/QC Requirement
Bin 1	Yes	Yes	Higher confidence –	10% by single reviewer; discrepancies resolved with second reviewer; repeat if >5% discrepancies
Bin 2	No	Yes	Less manual review needed	
Bin 3	Yes	No	Lower confidence –	20% by single reviewer; discrepancies resolved with second reviewer; repeat if >5% discrepancies
Bin 4	No	No	More manual review needed	

391

392 **Manual Review and Matching**

393 The mManual rReview and mMatching stage in the EHV curation workflow (Figure 1) apply
 394 to terms where computational processing did not result in any matches to existing EHV terms. Whereas
 395 QA/QC review described in the previous section compares paired sets of terms and hierarchical data to
 396 confirm matches, the purpose of manual review in this stage is to identify matches those computational
 397 methods failed to identify. To do this, expert reviewers compare 100 percent of the unmatched
 398 extracted terms to the EHV. The reviewers decide whether each extracted term matches an existing EHV
 399 term, has no match, or has inadequate data to support a decision (i.e., ambiguous). Extracted terms that
 400 the reviewers determine do not match any existing EHV terms will be considered ~~by EPA~~ as candidates
 401 for addition to the EHV.

402 When performing manual review and matching, expert reviewers will compare terms as well as
 403 the hierarchical data associated with the EHV and extracted terms, as available. Comparing the
 404 hierarchical data provides the expert reviewers with additional context to assess whether the endpoints
 405 terms represent the same concept. For example, nearly equivalent terms will be considered
 406 nonmatching if they are associated with different organs or organ systems in the EHV and extracted
 407 terms datasets. In addition, expert reviewers can filter the EHV data by hierarchical data fields to search
 408 for matches more efficiently. If an extracted term is associated with a particular hierarchical category
 409 (e.g., cardiovascular system), the reviewer can filter the EHV terms so that only cardiovascular endpoints
 410 are shown for comparison. To increase the efficiency of this step, an electronic reviewer form or other
 411 tool may be developed or adopted in the future to facilitate filtering and side-by-side data comparisons.

412 This manual review and matching stage will require expert knowledge of toxicological studies,
413 including study and exposure design, study methodology, human and animal physiology, and
414 toxicological health endpoints. The refore, manual review will be based on domain expert judgement ~~by~~
415 ~~PhD level assessment developers trained in US EPA assessment development practices according to the~~
416 ~~IRIS Handbook. The manual review requires expert judgement~~ due to incomplete hierarchical data, text
417 and conceptual ambiguities, and other data limitations. The basis for expert judgments will be
418 documented by reviewers as explanatory comments when appropriate to make transparent the
419 rationale for reviewer decisions in a suitable ontology management software.

420 For quality control, it may be advisable to require independent review of the matching decisions
421 by a second expert reviewer. The QA/QC approach, scope, and level of review should be decided
422 following a preliminary (e.g., spot-check) review of the initial matching and QA/QC results, including the
423 reviewer comments, the number of terms in the data set, and other factors. For example, depending on
424 the results of the preliminary review, full QA/QC of the expert review could require a second,
425 independent review of all terms, secondary review of a sample of terms, or secondary review focused
426 on matched terms, non-matched terms, or terms considered inconclusive by the primary reviewer.
427 Discrepancies between the primary and secondary reviewers should be resolved by a third reviewer.

428 The EHV Curation Workflow sorts HAWC extracted terms into two groups, including terms found
429 to have matches already in the EHV and terms determined to be absent from the EHV. The process for
430 curating these term groups to maintain the EHV is discussed below.

431 **Terms With EHV Matches**

432 A primary objective of the EHV Curation Workflow is to identify health endpoints that can be
433 added to the EHV. As shown in Figure 2, terms that are matched to EHV terms follow the pipeline to
434 curate hierarchical data and metadata. Terms that are already represented in the EHV are
435 excluded from further consideration, although these terms and associated hierarchical data are useful to
436 consider for refining the EHV. In the EHV curation steps, the hierarchical and other data associated with
437 the matching extracted terms can be used to complete EHV information for the existing terms. A
438 detailed sub workflow for this step has not yet been developed, but this sub workflow is expected to
439 reference existing resources such as the UMLS for missing information. Missing information may include
440 endpoint terms that lack complete hierarchical data, definitions, and identifiers such as UMLS concept
441 unique identifiers (CUI) and/or unique identifiers of semantic types (TUI), when available. As indicated
442 by the dashed line in Figure 2, the sub workflow would apply for curating hierarchical data and metadata
443 to existing EHV terms that were not matched to any of the extracted terms that entered the workflow.

444 The continued curation of EHV matching terms could be used to refine the efficiency of the
445 computational processing stage of the workflow. Specifically, new equivalent terms may be identified
446 from the EHV matching terms, which can be added to the cumulative equivalent~~s~~ dataset library. With
447 each application of the EHV Curation Workflow, extracted terms determined to equate to existing EHV
448 endpoints, along with their associated data and EHV counterparts, are added to this cumulative
449 equivalents dataset. In subsequent applications of the workflow, the rules-based script will compare
450 extracted terms entering the workflow to the cumulative equivalents dataset to find EHV matches
451 that were identified by previous application of the workflow to sets of extracted terms. This approach
452 may incrementally increase the efficiency and confidence of semi-automated, rules-based matching
453 when the workflow is applied to new sets of extracted terms. Rules-based matching using the
454 cumulative equivalents dataset has not yet been developed but could be added to the existing workflow
455 as a potential next step.

456 **Terms Without EHV Matches**

457 The EHV curation workflow employs a series of computational and manual steps to match
458 extracted terms to EHV endpoints. Terms that are unmatched after the completion of the workflow may
459 be potential new endpoints for addition to the EHV. As part of the expert review steps reviewers will
460 classify unmatched terms as either eligible health endpoints or ambiguous terms (e.g., not health
461 endpoints). Eligible endpoints recommended by the reviewers will undergo additional review to confirm
462 induction as new EHV endpoints.

463 As shown in Figure 2, the terms without EHV matches progress toward addition to the EHV via
464 the normalize terms step. Normalizing a new EHV term means selecting the precise word or phrase
465 that will be used to consistently represent the new health endpoint concept. Normalization may be
466 needed if there are various forms (i.e., plural or singular) of words or phrases that are commonly used to
467 represent the same concept (e.g., white blood cells, WBC, monocytes or alanine aminotransferase, ALT,
468 serum glutamic, pyruvic transaminase, SGPT). To promote interoperability among tools and datasets,
469 the UMLS and/or other relevant ontologies will be used to identify normalized terms and phrases, as
470 available. If normalized terms are not found in other relevant ontologies, the most appropriate form of
471 the term will be selected for use in the EHV.

472 **Challenges and Limitations**

473 Currently implementation of the workflow is limited because some EHV endpoints are missing
474 metadata and/or definitions. For example, SciSpacy uses metadata and definitions to link endpoints to
475 biomedical ontologies and other knowledgebases (including UMLS). If these metadata and definitions

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476 are missing, SciSpacy may fail to correctly identify correct terms. Further, missing metadata and
477 definitions provide context, that when missing, can lead to inaccuracies in linking relationships between
478 terms and in identifying correct concepts from probed knowledgebases. Through iterative EHV is
479 curation of the EHV, it is expected that these data gaps will lessen, increasing performance of the
480 computational text processing steps and increase efficiency by reducing the overall time needed for
481 manual curation. Therefore, a critical next step will include data gap filling (including hierarchical
482 metadata and definitions) of the current EHV.

483 The need for lack of domain expertise is also a possible challenge to the workflow. Non-experts
484 may lack knowledge on the current standards and conventions in environmental health science and,
485 struggleing to accurately curate terms possibly leading to inconsistencies, data gaps, ambiguity, missing
486 hierarchical data, and or missing definitions. These inaccuracies could feedback on computational
487 processing steps, impeding performance or introducing inaccuracies that decrease trustworthiness and
488 interoperability with other terminology resources.

489 Therefore, aAgreed upon data standards for vocabularies and ontologies within a complex
490 domain are proactive solutions that can be adopted by a community working together to ensure
491 consistency, quality, accessibility and exchange of data. The true challenge will continue to be the
492 continued curation of these metadata and maintenance of a pool of domain experts as data sets and
493 ontologies are developed. A decentralized model for data curation within a trusted community of
494 domain experts is needed to bridge knowledge gaps and may be achieved through training, community
495 building, tooling, and incentives.

496 **Next Steps**

497 Implementation of the EHV Curation Workflow is currently undergoing additional development
498 and testing to include automation tools using an ontology management software application. For this
499 use case the Graphite Taxonomy and Ontology Management system was selected as the software
500 application to manage both the source vocabulary as well as the curation. The ontology management
501 software is specific for ontologies and allows modeling from multiple terminology resources, capturing
502 provenance during curation while allowing terminology changes back to other software (such as HAWC)
503 after curation. Through implementation of the curation workflow, detailed sub workflows will be
504 developed for curation and standardization of hierarchical metadata for EHV terms. The metadata is
505 needed to improve the performance of some of the computational scripts (e.g. SciSpacy) that are
506 currently limited by lack of metadata such as term definitions that will additionally expand the

507 computational processing stage to match extracted terms using the ~~c~~Cumulative ~~e~~Equivalents ~~d~~Dataset.
508 Anticipated improvements will also be realized as the ontology software should provide a user-friendly
509 interface for ~~users~~ QA/QC that is web accessible, possibly allowing crowdsourcing and asynchronous
510 collaboration. Since the EHV is the language standard for reporting animal health effects information in
511 human health assessments conducted by EPA CPAD and is made publicly available as a download as well
512 as via the publicly available HAWC application, it is envisaged that the EHV can help to standardize the
513 way findings are reported across the environmental health community. We anticipate engaging with the
514 broader environmental health science community to ensure not only standardization of the language,
515 but also coverage of biomedical science and other knowledge domains reported in the literature, but
516 not yet covered by the EHV. The EHV is currently machine actionable meaning that it is “AI ready” ~~and is~~
517 ~~currently being used as a vocabulary resources in data extraction workbenches such as LaserAI (Angrish~~
518 ~~et. al., 2025)~~. We anticipate ~~the future opportunity~~ future updates to the curation workflow will
519 incorporate to move beyond into generative AI capabilities, going beyond large language models by
520 supplementing them with retrieval augmented generation (RAG) generative AI to take a deeper dive
521 into the more specific topics that describe environmental health science.

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Figures

1a)

1b)

Figure 1A and B. A) The environmental Health Vocabulary (EHV) is a five-level hierarchy to describe health effects within assessments. Currently the EHV describes animal health effects. The only implementation of the EHV is within HAWC and is available at <https://hawv.epa.gov/vocab/ehv>. B) The EHV enables a visual summary of endpoints aggregated by health system (hepatic) and organ (liver).

Figure 2

Figure 2. Environmental health vocabulary (EHV) curation workflow. The curation workflow is presented in stages that include computational text processing (preprocess text, exact string match, rules-based script, and SciSpacy), QA/QC of computational matches, manual review and matching followed by QA/QC, and curation of the EHV data.

1 Figure 3

2
3 Figure 3. QA of matching terms. Hierarchical data enable to terms to be sorted into four bins based
4 on the completeness of the hierarchical data and the data match/mismatch. Bins 1 and 2 receive a
5 partial review whereas bins 3 and 4 receive a more complete review.

6